

Project name	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project acronym	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project number	101131809
Deliverable no	4.2
Deliverable title	Literature Gap Analysis Review
Contractual delivery month	M23
Responsible partner	ECRIN
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Dissemination level	Public
Description of deliverable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scoping Literature Review on Gaps in Service Provision to Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC) • Consolidated Gap Analysis, considering feedback from service providers, secohort users and the results of the scoping literature review. • Stakeholder Consultation Workshop on Gap Prioritisation

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Full Term
BBMRI-ERIC	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EBRAINS	European Brain Research Infrastructures
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CHNAA	Community Health Needs and Assets Assessments
CRF	Case Report Form
COS	Core Outcome Sets
CRedit	Contributor Roles Taxonomy
CYP	Children and Young People
DAGs	Direct Acyclic Graphs
DEI	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DOIs	Digital Object Identifiers
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHRs	Electronic Health Records
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EUREC	European Network of Research Ethics Committees
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HL7	Health Level Seven
ICD-10	International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, 10th Revision
IC	Informed Consent
IPD-MAs	Individual Patient Data Meta-Analyses
LLMs	Large Language Models
LMedC	Large Medical Cohort
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names & Codes
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OFICA2	Observatoire Français de l'Insuffisance Cardiaque Aiguë 2
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
DataSHIELD	Data Aggregation through Anonymous Summary-statistics from Harmonised Individual-level Lifecourse Data
OMICS	High-throughput “-omics” disciplines
PPI	Patient and Public Involvement
QA/QC	Quality Assurance and Quality Control
RWD	Real World Data

RWE	Real World Evidence
SNDS	Système National des Données de Santé
SNOMED-CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SPEs	Secure Processing Environments
TREs	Trusted Research Environments
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

Work Package 4 (WP4), “The Current European Research Infrastructure (RI) Landscape”, examines how existing international, European and national research infrastructures support the design, implementation, long-term operation, and reuse of Large Medical Cohorts (LMedCs), with the overarching aim of informing the development of a more coherent, efficient, and sustainable infrastructure ecosystem in Europe. Deliverable D4.2 presents a comprehensive gap analysis of services supporting LMedCs in Europe.

Methodology

The gap analysis followed a **four-step**, mixed-methods approach. First, existing infrastructure services were mapped through *surveys* and *interviews* with 25 service-providing organisations, complemented by in-depth discussions with infrastructure representatives. Second, service user needs were assessed via *semi-structured interviews* with users, including researchers, cohort managers, and patient representatives from multiple European countries. Third, a scoping literature review of studies focused on identifying service gaps and stakeholder needs was conducted, resulting in 76 eligible publications that were systematically analysed. Finally, findings from these activities were triangulated and refined through a multi-stakeholder consultation workshop involving approximately 30 participants, who reviewed, validated, and prioritised the identified gaps.

To ensure coherence and analytical clarity, all gaps and needs were organised into five overarching service clusters: 1) Data Services, 2) Regulatory and Ethical Support Services, 3) Methodology and Design Services, 4) Biobanking and OMICS Services, and 5) Operational Support and Coordination Services.

Results

Literature Review

The scoping literature review confirms that many challenges faced by large medical cohorts are systemic and recurrent across disease areas and study designs. Key issues identified in the literature include persistent weaknesses in data standardisation, harmonisation, and interoperability; insufficient data completeness and quality assurance; limited cohort discoverability and poor metadata availability; and underdeveloped federated and privacy-preserving data infrastructures. Regulatory and ethical challenges are also prominent, particularly fragmented implementation of GDPR and other ELSI requirements, outdated and static informed consent models, and limited institutional capacity to support complex, cross-border data reuse.

Methodological shortcomings include weak protocol registration and feasibility assessment, heterogeneous analytical workflows, limited transparency in causal inference, and inadequate integration of patient and public involvement. In biobanking and OMICS research, challenges include inconsistent quality control, lack of harmonised protocols, limited diversity and representation, and fragile sustainability of infrastructures. Operationally, recruitment, retention, coordination, and workforce alignment are under-supported yet critical determinants of cohort success.

Consolidated Gap Analysis

By integrating evidence from service providers, service users, the literature review, and stakeholder feedback, the consolidated gap analysis identifies and prioritises key service gaps across the five clusters. The top-ten priorities according to the stakeholders are:

- 1) Data Standardization, Harmonization, and Interoperability*
- 2) (Cohort) Data Discoverability, Metadata Availability and Quality*
- 3) Data Completeness and Data Quality*
- 4) Inconsistent ELSI Requirements Across Jurisdictions*
- 5) Harmonised Processes and Tools*
- 6) Inadequate Participant Recruitment and Retention Strategies*
- 7) Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in Biobanking and OMICS*
- 8) Workforce Limitations and Misalignment between Clinical and Research Operations*
- 9) Inclusion of Biobanking and OMICS Analysis in Cohort Studies*
- 10) Protocol Registration and Feasibility Assessment*

Recommendations

Based on the prioritised gaps, Deliverable D4.2 formulates strategic, high-level recommendations to guide policymakers, funders and researchers. These include:

- 1) Ensuring long-term financial sustainability of cohorts and supporting infrastructures.*
- 2) Promoting regulatory and ethical harmonisation across jurisdictions.*
- 3) Advancing data standardisation, interoperability, and metadata quality.*
- 4) Strengthening methodological rigor and transparency.*
- 5) Expanding capacity for federated and privacy-preserving data analysis.*
- 6) Improving biobanking and multi-omics quality, harmonisation, and representativeness.*
- 7) Establishing coordinated operational support structures for cohorts.*
- 8) Addressing workforce shortages and building multidisciplinary expertise.*
- 9) Promoting inclusive, participant-centred research practices.*
- 10) Reforming incentive structures to reward open, collaborative, and infrastructure-oriented science.*

Outlook

The WP4 gap analysis shows that, although multiple service providers for Large Medical Cohorts operate at international, European, and national levels and collectively cover the full lifecycle of cohort studies, service provision remains fragmented, often lacking scalability and effective coordination. Cohort service users frequently face challenges in discovering available services and understanding how to access them, reflecting limited visibility and engagement across the relevant research communities. Addressing these challenges does not require the creation of new infrastructures; rather, it calls for reinforcing collaboration, integration, and harmonization among existing providers. Establishing a coordinated and comprehensive service package that brings together relevant European (e.g., ECRIN, BBMRI, ELIXIR, Euro-BioImaging, EBRAINS) and national service providers, paired with clear and user-friendly access pathways, would effectively bridge most of the gaps identified. Such an approach would strengthen the long-term sustainability, resilience, and scientific impact of Large Medical Cohorts by fostering a more connected and supportive ecosystem. The insights from WP4 will be actively discussed with the leaders and partners of WP16 “New Concept and Sustainability”.

INTRODUCTION

This section introduces Work Package (WP) 4 “The Current European RI Landscape”, provides the working definition of Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC) and defines the scope of deliverable D4.2 “Literature Gap Analysis Review”.

WP4: THE CURRENT EUROPEAN RI-LANDSCAPE

WP4 focuses on the current European RI-landscape and has the following objectives:

1. Describe the European landscape of Research Infrastructures (RI) and relevant projects/initiatives and identify the current infrastructure support to the design, planning, conduct and exploitation of large medical cohorts (Task 4.1);
2. Identify the service users’ needs, in terms of infrastructure tools and services: cohort operators, cohort data re-users, funders and key stakeholders (Task 4.2);
3. **Compare the infrastructure service offer and the service user needs to conduct a gap analysis, contributing to the strategy towards a comprehensive research infrastructure coverage for large medical cohorts (Task 4.3).**

DEFINITION OF LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS

Earlier work within WP3 “Large medical cohorts to build on” provided a definition for Large Medical Cohorts that is used across the different INTEGRATE-LMedC tasks.

“A medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic or exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. We consider a medical cohort as “large” in the following circumstances:

- *A clinical cohort (observational) comprising over 1.000 participants selected for a health condition; or*
- *A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or*
- *A population cohort comprising over 10.000 participants.”*

SCOPE OF DELIVERABLE 4.2

Deliverable 4.2 aims to systematically identify, analyze, and present the key gaps between existing infrastructure services for large medical cohorts and the actual needs of service

users and the broader European research community. The report is further informed by a targeted literature review and enriched by insights from a stakeholder consultation workshop involving experts across multiple domains of cohort research. Together, these inputs ensure that the resulting recommendations are grounded in both evidence and community perspectives.

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY FOR THE GAP ANALYSIS

The gap analysis was carried out in four steps:

- **Mapping existing infrastructure services:** WP4 catalogued the services, tools, and capacities offered by national, pan-European, and selected international infrastructures supporting large medical cohorts across the full research data lifecycle—from study design and governance to long-term data exploitation. A targeted survey was completed by 25 organisations, and 23 of them participated in follow-up interviews. These findings are described in detail in [D4.1 “Mapping of available infrastructure services for Large Medical Cohorts”](#).
- **Assessing service user needs:** A qualitative study using semi-structured interviews with key service user groups (researchers, cohort managers, project managers and patient representatives) was conducted to identify needs related to accessing, using, and sustaining cohort resources. Eleven interviewees from seven European countries contributed to this assessment. The full results are reported in [M2 “Mapping of user needs in terms of infrastructure services for large medical cohorts”](#).
- **Scoping Literature Review:** A scoping review of the literature was conducted to validate the findings from the service-provider mapping and service user-needs assessment. This step ensured that any additional services or needs not identified in the earlier stages could be captured, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of the European landscape.
- **Stakeholder Consultation Workshop:** A draft gap analysis, integrating insights from all preceding steps, was shared with 30 key stakeholders ahead of a consultation workshop held on 14 November 2025. The workshop focused on reviewing the identified service gaps, identifying any missing elements, and prioritising the gaps to guide further strategic planning.

Figure 1 shows the four-step methodology followed by the INTEGRATE-LMedC partners for

the gap analysis.

Figure 1 Four-step methodology for the gap analysis of services for Large Medical Cohorts

CATEGORISATION IN SERVICE CLUSTERS

To facilitate a structured and coherent gap analysis, the WP4 partners decided to thematically organise the identified service gaps and user needs into five overarching service clusters. These five clusters reflect the main functional domains that support the lifecycle of large medical cohorts:

1. Data Services

Support the full data lifecycle including data harmonization and standards, data management plan, monitoring, cohort data secondary use, cohort data sharing, biostatistics and data analysis, case report form (CRF) development, and data quality control. These services underpin the discoverability, interoperability, and secure reuse of cohort data across the research ecosystem.

2. Regulatory and Ethical Support Services

Covering guidance and support for compliance with ethical standards, data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR), governance processes, and legal frameworks. This includes services that facilitate responsible data sharing, consent management, and cross-border collaboration.

3. Methodology and Design Services

Including support for study design, statistical expertise, methodological consultation, and best-practice guidance across the research lifecycle. These services underpin the scientific quality and robustness of cohort studies.

4. Biobanking and OMICS Services

Encompassing the infrastructure and expertise required for the collection, processing, storage, and management of biological samples, as well as associated OMICS data (e.g., genomics, proteomics, metabolomics). These services enable

integration of molecular data with cohort information.

5. Operational Support and Coordination Services

This cluster encompasses project coordination, study implementation support, access/navigation assistance, patient recruitment and patient engagement services, dissemination and user training and capacity-building services.

Annex 1 provides a detailed list of services that have been grouped under each thematic cluster. This categorisation ensures a consistent analytical framework and supports clear identification of gaps, overlaps, and priority areas for future service development across the European large medical cohort landscape.

Figure 2 Categorisation of service gaps in five clusters

METHODOLOGY FOR THE SCOPING LITERATURE REVIEW

This section outlines the methodology used for the scoping literature review.

Research question

To align with and complement the findings from the preceding WP4 activities, the literature review was guided by two overarching research questions:

- i) *What gaps exist in the current provision of services to Large Medical Cohorts (LMedCs)?*
- ii) *What are the needs of cohort service users?*

Information sources

PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) was the literature database used for this scoping review.

Eligibility criteria

Table 1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the scoping review

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	Articles published in English	Articles published in any language other than English
Publication date	Articles published in the period 2020-2025	Articles published before 1 January 2020
Full text availability	Free full text available, free of charge	Articles available only behind a paywall
Species	Human studies	Animal studies
Geographic focus	Studies conducted in Europe	Studies conducted exclusively outside Europe
Scientific domain	Primary focus on life sciences: biology, medicine, biomedicine. Articles from other scientific domains (e.g., environmental sciences, social sciences and humanities) may be included if their relevance to life sciences is explicitly described and judged by the reviewers (case-by-case assessment).	Articles, without a clear or direct applicability to life sciences from other scientific domains (e.g., environmental sciences, social sciences and humanities).
Content focus	<p>Two types of articles will be included:</p> <p>i) Articles whose primary topic relates to at least one of the five predefined service clusters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data Services ▪ Regulatory and Ethical Support ▪ Methodology and Design ▪ Biobanking and Omics ▪ Operational Support and Coordination <p>ii) Articles describing clinical studies, provided they explicitly report on stakeholder needs,</p>	<p>i) Articles whose topic cannot be classified under one of the five service clusters.</p> <p>ii) Articles that do not report on stakeholder needs; perspectives or service gaps or barriers or</p>

	perspectives, barriers or challenges.	challenges iii) Articles describing clinical studies but without mentioning needs or challenges.
Study Design	Cohort Studies, Observational studies (Longitudinal, Prospective and Retrospective)	Clinical trials, interventional studies, registries
Study Size	Clinical Cohorts comprising at least 1000 participants; Population Cohorts comprising at least 10,000 participants	Studies with smaller population size are excluded.
Study Follow-up	Studies with follow-up	Studies without follow-up

Search strategy

The following Boolean search strategy was applied for the identification of relevant literature:

(cohort[tiab] OR "cohort study"[tiab] OR "follow-up study"[tiab] OR longitudinal*[tiab] OR prospective*[tiab] OR retrospective*[tiab]) AND ("Data Management"[MeSH Terms] OR data manag*[tiab] OR "Data Sharing"[tiab] OR "Data Harmonization"[tiab] OR "Ethics"[MeSH Terms] OR ethical[tiab] OR legal[tiab] OR social[tiab] OR ELSI[tiab] OR "Research Design"[MeSH Terms] OR "study methodology"[tiab]) AND (needs[tiab] OR services[tiab] OR gaps[tiab] OR challenges[tiab] OR barriers[tiab] OR perspectives[tiab] OR disparities[tiab] OR inequity[tiab]) NOT (trial[ti] OR trials[ti] OR registry[ti] OR registries[ti])*

After applying the filtering criteria in line with the eligibility requirements described above, the search yielded **1,466 publications**. Titles and abstracts were screened independently by two non-blinded reviewers to assess eligibility according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria presented in Table 1. Each publication was classified as *Included*, *Excluded*, or *Maybe*.

When there was agreement between the two reviewers, the publications were processed as follows:

- If both reviewers marked a record as *Included*, it was moved to the full-text screening phase.
- If both reviewers marked a record as *Excluded*, it was removed from the review.
- If both reviewers marked a record as *Maybe*, a consensus meeting would be planned to decide upon the inclusion or exclusion of the resource.

For records where the reviewers disagreed, the following decision rules were applied:

- **Included + Maybe** → **Included**: The publication proceeded to full-text screening.
- **Excluded + Maybe** → **Excluded**: The publication was removed.
- **Included + Excluded** → **Consensus meeting**: A discussion was held to reach agreement on inclusion or exclusion.

This process resulted in **1341 publications excluded**, with **125 publications** advancing to the full-text screening phase.

During full-text screening, the publications were divided between the two reviewers. For any publication considered unsuitable for inclusion, the reviewer documented a justification. Common reasons for exclusion included:

- Geographical focus outside Europe or non-European settings.
- Cohort sizes inconsistent with the project's definition of Large Medical Cohorts (LMedCs).
- Lack of relevance to service gaps or service user needs.
- Studies without follow-up or not involving longitudinal cohorts.

Following full-text review, **76 publications** met the eligibility criteria and were included in the scoping review for data extraction.

The full scoping review process, including the number of records at each stage, is summarised in the PRISMA flow diagram presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 PRISMA flow diagram describing the different steps of the scoping review

RESULTS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW

The 76 publications included in the scoping review were divided between the two reviewers for data charting. For each publication, reviewers extracted information on service gaps mapped to the five predefined service clusters (Data Services; Regulatory and Ethical Support Services; Methodology and Design Services; Biobanking and OMICS Services; and Operational Support and Coordination Services), as well as any identified user needs. The structure of the data charting table is provided in Annex2.

AI tools (ChatGPT and Perplexity AI) were employed to assist in summarizing the extracted information. This process was conducted under the supervision of the two reviewers to ensure the accuracy and fidelity of the summaries.

1. GAPS IN DATA SERVICES

In the literature, several gaps related to data services were identified.

Data Completeness and Data Quality

A pervasive issue across real-world data (RWD) and real-world evidence (RWE) sources is the lack of standardized, continuous, and quality-controlled data collection [1]. The fragmentation of health information systems and the absence of routine validated data capture mechanisms lead to incomplete records and introduce systemic biases. Tools for detecting, managing or imputing missing data are insufficient, and where they exist, they risk introducing further bias [1]. The absence of robust, cross-source quality assurance frameworks severely limits the reproducibility and reliability of research outcomes.

Epidemiological data collected during crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, exemplify these shortcomings: inconsistencies in temporal structures, case definitions, and reporting practices hinder comparability. In addition, lack of data permanence was observed, with multiple agencies across Europe generating statistics during the pandemic providing only current epidemiological data but not archived versions of previous days/weeks/months, making retrospective analysis and replication difficult [2], [3]. Similarly, the French OFICA2 study that embedded linkage with the Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS) for the participant follow-up, highlights temporal gaps, as healthcare data become accessible only two years after collection, impeding real-time analyses [4]. A study on Zika virus highlighted that the variable metadata quality was a major issue. Study protocols were evolving during a pandemic situation and datasets suffered from incomplete or inconsistent reporting of laboratory procedures and definitions [5]. Routine clinical datasets further suffer from validation deficits due to coding variability and lack of longitudinal follow-up [6]. These issues underscore an urgent need for automated, standardized data quality monitoring services capable of real-time anomaly detection, version control, and continuous validation.

Data Standardization, Harmonization, and Interoperability

A critical deficiency in health data services lies in the absence of consistent standards for data formats, terminologies, and metadata across regions and systems [1], [7]. Weak interoperability between disparate real-world data sources—such as electronic health records (EHRs), registries, and claims databases—creates silos that inhibit integration [1]. This problem extends to specialized research domains, where heterogeneous acquisition protocols and analytical pipelines result in irreproducible findings. In multi-site imaging studies and ML applications, variations in scanner parameters, hardware, and preprocessing software further compromise data harmonization [8].

Federated and multinational research networks report similar challenges, with retrospective harmonization across nodes proving resource-intensive and error-prone [9], [10], [11], [12]. Disparate data models (OMOP, HL7 FHIR), inconsistent vocabularies (LOINC, SNOMED CT, ICD-10), and differing quality assurance procedures obstruct comparability and reproducibility [13] [14]. Efforts to merge data retrospectively, as in HealthData@EU pilots, reveal extensive variability in access procedures and metadata completeness [11]. These recurring issues indicate that a comprehensive, service-oriented approach to data standardization and interoperability—supported by automated mapping tools and unified data dictionaries—is essential for sustainable data integration.

Survey data are important in biomedical, clinical, behavioral and social studies but pose significant challenges to reproducibility. Inconsistencies arise from multiple factors, including variability in translations across languages, differences in how constructs are operationalized, selective inclusion of questionnaire components, variations in clinical diagnosis criteria, and inconsistencies in versioning across research teams and time points. Widely used survey platforms do not inherently enforce assessment standardization, version control, or interoperability across research teams and time points. In addition, there is lack of a structured framework for defining, managing, and versioning questionnaires at the point of data collection [15].

Similarly, neuroimaging databases often lack standardized metadata schemas and indexing systems, hindering efficient retrieval and integration [8]. In rheumatology and cardiology studies, data from different care providers remain siloed, preventing longitudinal patient tracking and comprehensive analysis [16]. Similar fragmentation is evident in mental health, where multimodal time-series data are inconsistently collected and poorly harmonized, restricting generalizability [17].

Individual Participant Data Linkage across different databases

The ability to link individual patient data across sources is a defining feature of high-quality data ecosystems, yet remains poorly implemented [1]. Many systems lack robust tokenization or patient identity linkage services that ensure secure and accurate cross-database integration. Infrastructure for linking records while preserving privacy is fragmented and inconsistent across countries [1]. The French OFICA2 and FRENCHIE cohorts demonstrate the benefits of robust linkage to the SNDS for longitudinal tracking but also reveal constraints: reliance on unique national identifiers ensures matching accuracy but limits accessibility due to regulatory restrictions and privacy concerns. The linkage to SNDS allows the automated and exhaustive collection of: All-cause and cause-specific mortality, Hospital admissions and procedures (inpatient and outpatient), Medication use and reimbursements, Healthcare consumption and medico-economic data [4], [18].

These barriers are compounded by the absence of cross-border interoperability frameworks that support privacy-preserving record linkage. The current ecosystem lacks services offering cryptographically secure tokenization and deduplication mechanisms compliant with GDPR and similar regulations.

Robustness and generalizability of ML and AI models

Limited service offerings exist for identifying or mitigating selection, recall, and detection bias in RWD and AI applications [1]. In machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP), algorithms often rely on incomplete or biased datasets, confirming existing hypotheses rather than generating new insights [19], [20]. Studies in gastroenterology, multiple sclerosis, and oncology show that limited data representativeness and inconsistent sampling criteria lead to models with poor generalizability and reproducibility [13], [21], [22].

Moreover, governance tools to dynamically monitor and correct bias within data pipelines are largely absent [1]. Ethical and inclusivity gaps are evident in AI for mental health and

extended reality therapies, where algorithmic bias and the exclusion of marginalized populations persist [23]. These challenges demand a new generation of governance-oriented services—integrating bias auditing, model transparency, explainable AI frameworks, and inclusive data design—to ensure fairness and accountability across the data lifecycle.

Computational Infrastructure and Reproducibility

Across clinical domains, computational infrastructure for large-scale AI and ML research remains inadequate. Many institutions lack the hardware and scalable environments necessary for training advanced models, particularly deep neural networks that require vast datasets [24]. Existing pipelines are rarely reproducible, with limited use of standardized environments or containerization frameworks [21], [22]. In oncology and imaging, the scarcity of open-access repositories for both datasets and implementation code further limits validation and transparency [21], [22].

Furthermore, few centralized facilities exist for standardized model testing or benchmarking. In the UK, for example, the lack of national “AI Labs” impedes independent validation of clinical AI tools [25]. The absence of such infrastructure perpetuates methodological fragmentation, limiting reproducibility, comparability, and regulatory confidence.

Federated Data Infrastructure

Federated data architectures are increasingly recognized as critical to cross-border research, yet implementation challenges remain extensive. Studies show substantial variability in technical configurations, data access processes, and security protocols among federated nodes [11]. Data synchronization is often delayed, with incomplete updates across systems, while identity management processes are inefficient and prolong access times [9]. In federated analyses, such as those under HealthData@EU and EHDS pilots, harmonization demands significant manual intervention and introduces analytical biases [11], [12].

The lack of harmonized fee structures, access procedures, and open-access synthetic datasets exacerbates fragmentation [11]. Technical disparities between nodes—such as inconsistent organizational and information security standards—limit scalability and reproducibility. Without standardized orchestration and automated harmonization pipelines, federated infrastructures risk remaining costly, fragmented prototypes rather than sustainable operational systems.

FAIR Data Management and Discoverability

Despite increasing adoption of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, implementation remains inconsistent. Many datasets lack persistent identifiers, metadata schemas, and standardized cataloguing mechanisms, reducing discoverability and reuse [8]. As exemplified by a study in aging research, information on cohort studies and their variables is scattered across repositories and publications, requiring extensive manual searches [26]. In addition, as reported in another study focusing on secondary use of Individual Participant Data (IPD) in meta-analysis for infectious diseases, findability of

cohorts was a complex and time-consuming task. It often consists of systematic searches in peer-reviewed and grey literature followed by e-mail exchanges with publication authors to clarify conditions of re-use. As an indication the authors of the publication identified and contacted 108 relevant studies, out of which 35 responded (41%) and out of which 8 datasets were ultimately shared [27]. Common reasons for refusal:

- *Data loss/destruction, PI retirement, or institutional restrictions.*
- *Concerns about data misuse or misinterpretation.*
- *Lack of credit or recognition for sharing.*

Offering co-authorship and recognition helped encourage participation [27].

The Healthy Ageing Toolkit (<https://www.healthyageing-toolkit.cepar.edu.au/>) provides an example of how searchable repositories can address these deficiencies by consolidating metadata and enabling cross-national comparisons [26]. However, many fields—particularly mental health, epidemiology, and survey-based research—still operate without structured frameworks for version control and dataset provenance [15], [17]. Comprehensive FAIR-compliant data services, offering automated metadata generation, persistent identifiers (DOIs), and cross-repository search functionality, are urgently needed to support transparency and long-term stewardship.

Training

Finally, the lack of methodological support and professional training represents a persistent bottleneck across biomedical data ecosystems. Clinicians and researchers often lack sufficient education in ML and NLP methods, reducing their ability to interpret and apply AI systems effectively [19]. Explainable AI remains underdeveloped, with most models functioning as “black boxes” without transparent interpretability frameworks [19], [23]. Addressing these deficiencies requires institutionalized training programs, methodological standardization services, and the integration of explainable, interpretable AI systems that can be understood and communicated by clinicians to patients.

2. GAPS IN REGULATORY AND ETHICAL SUPPORT SERVICES

In the literature, several gaps related to regulatory and ethical support services were identified.

Fragmented and Inconsistent Regulatory Frameworks Across Jurisdictions

Regulatory and ethical frameworks for health research—particularly those involving AI, real-world data (RWD), and international collaboration—remain fragmented, inconsistent, and insufficiently harmonized across countries and institutions.

- Regulatory bodies acknowledge the importance of real-world evidence (RWE), but researchers still lack clear and consistent guidance on how to use real-world data (RWD) in regulatory applications [1].
- The absence of an enforceable global standard similar to GDPR complicates cross-border collaboration and data sharing, especially when ethical oversight and

regulatory rigor vary substantially among jurisdictions. For example, Germany mandates robust, multidisciplinary ethics committees with lay representation, while in China, the structure and enforcement of ethics oversight are uneven and variably applied. China's data protection standards remain less stringent than the EU's GDPR, which results in divergent practices for participant privacy and data security [28].

Such fragmentation impedes international research collaboration, increases administrative burden, and creates uncertainty for investigators.

Deficiencies in Informed Consent Models and Implementation

The text highlights pervasive issues with the design, communication, and operationalization of informed consent (IC).

a) Outdated static models

Traditional, one-time consent models are ill-equipped to handle dynamic research environments, such as stem cell applications, data reuse, or evolving AI systems. The validity of previously obtained consent is questioned in light of new scientific developments [29]. Static IC approaches cannot accommodate ongoing participant preferences or future uses of biospecimens and data.

b) Limited clarity and comprehension

Consent documents are often too complex for general literacy levels and fail to adequately inform participants about future data reuse or transfer of biological materials [30]. Participants frequently lose connection with their data or receive no future updates, violating international ethical principles of transparency and autonomy.

c) Challenges in electronic and hybrid consenting

Implementation of electronic informed consent (e-consent) faces several operational and regulatory barriers:

- Lack of harmonized regulatory frameworks across jurisdictions for reviewing, storing, and inspecting e-consent [30].
- Limited digital competence among ethics committees evaluating e-consent materials.
- Unclear legal validity for dynamic consent models under differing privacy laws.
- Insufficient hybrid options combining digital and paper-based systems, excluding participants with limited digital access or literacy [28].

d) Equity and Accessibility Gaps

In Germany, lack of multilingual consent processes and adaptive materials excludes non-German speakers and low-literacy populations from participation in anaesthesia-related research [31]. Similar barriers appear in other contexts, where standardised procedures hinder patient-centred communication.

Modernized consent frameworks—such as dynamic or tiered consent—must replace static models to reflect continuous data use and evolving research contexts.

Lack of Equity, Inclusion, and Stakeholder Engagement

Equity in participation and stakeholder inclusion are underdeveloped within regulatory and ethical infrastructures.

- Underrepresented groups, such as Indigenous peoples and rural populations, face systemic barriers to genomic testing and are poorly represented in datasets [32].
- The absence of adaptive communication infrastructures (interpreters, visual materials, or simplified language) disproportionately excludes low-literacy and linguistically diverse populations from informed participation [31], [33].

Equity must become a guiding principle in ethical oversight, ensuring diverse representation and meaningful patient involvement.

Inadequate Institutional Support for Legal and Regulatory Navigation

Institutions often lack in-house legal expertise and operational support for compliance with complex ethical and regulatory requirements.

- Research teams in infectious disease projects had to engage external legal experts to manage cross-border data-sharing approvals [27].
- Similar challenges appear in AI-based or data-intensive research, where operational costs and compliance management are significant burdens [29].

Regulatory and ethical support services should include specialized legal units capable of navigating multi-jurisdictional compliance, data governance, and participant protection. Without such infrastructure, researchers face costly, fragmented, and delayed ethical approval processes.

Emerging Ethical Gaps from AI and Digital Health Technologies

The rapid adoption of AI and digital platforms has outpaced existing ethical and regulatory frameworks.

- In psychiatry, AI use raises issues of confidentiality, algorithmic transparency, and potential overreach in clinical recommendations [19].
- In nephrology and colorectal cancer management, algorithmic bias, safety validation, and accountability mechanisms remain insufficiently defined [27], [34], [35].
- Digital health tools, such as e-health platforms, transform data processing practices and challenge conventional notions of consent and participant autonomy [29].

Regulators must develop adaptive frameworks capable of evaluating algorithmic transparency, bias mitigation, and the ethical governance of digital systems.

Training

Ethics committees and oversight bodies often lack the training, digital literacy, and

procedural guidance necessary to evaluate complex or technology-driven research proposals.

- Ethics committee members demonstrate limited familiarity with electronic systems and insufficient regulatory guidance for evaluating multimedia consent or participant identification procedures [30].
- In international collaborations (e.g., with China or other similar jurisdictions), ethics committees might lack robust mechanisms to address ethical violations, and enforcement of existing regulations remains inconsistent [28].
- Even within advanced systems, oversight bodies face uncertainty in interpreting ethical implications of novel technologies such as large language models (LLMs) in nephrology, where algorithmic bias, data accuracy, and accountability are unresolved [27], [35].

3. GAPS IN METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN SERVICES

In the literature, several gaps related to methodology and design services were identified.

Limited Community Integration and Participatory Foundations

Community-based approaches such as Community Health Needs and Assets Assessments (CHNAA) are underused, despite their potential to enhance public trust and improve research relevance. Insufficient integration of community engagement frameworks weakens research design from the earliest stages, resulting in studies that may not reflect real population needs or priorities. Increased use of CHNAA could guide topic selection, ensure inclusivity, and build public confidence in research [36].

Additionally, Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) often suffers from tokenistic inclusion, where contributions are superficial rather than integral to decision-making [37], [38]. Barriers include limited resources, unclear communication, and researcher skepticism about PPI's value. Similarly, for children and young people (CYP), PPI is often confined to narrow stages (design or data collection) and rarely extends to governance or priority-setting, reflecting structural gaps in co-production methodology [39].

Inadequate Multidisciplinary and Multivariate Integration in Aging Research

Aging research illustrates broader methodological limitations in multivariate study design. Current designs often fail to disentangle the effects of chronological age, birth cohort, and time of measurement, resulting in confounded interpretations [40].

There is also a lack of standardized longitudinal measures aligned with frameworks such as the WHO Healthy Ageing model, limiting comparability across cohorts [26]. Furthermore, crucial domains such as housing and neighborhood environments are under-measured, impeding comprehensive understanding of ageing determinants [26].

Gender-sensitive methodology is also insufficiently embedded in study designs, particularly regarding recruitment, flexible participation modes, and communication strategies [41].

Persistent Biases and Confounding in Observational and Cohort Studies

Non-randomized designs inherently suffer from bias due to unmeasured or imbalanced covariates [42], [43], [44]. While strategies such as restriction, stratification, multivariate regression, and propensity score matching are used, their application is inconsistent and often methodologically weak [45].

Common problems include:

- Incomplete covariate adjustment, with missing key demographic or clinical variables.
- Over-restriction reducing generalizability.
- Insufficient power in stratified analyses.
- Bias from unmeasured confounders, particularly in socioeconomic or clinical domains [45].

Despite the availability of tools such as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) or machine learning phenotyping, their systematic use in bias mitigation is rare.

Insufficient Standardization and Harmonization of Outcomes

There is no agreed-upon methodology for identifying primary and secondary outcomes across studies, nor for harmonizing them to support future interventional research [46].

This fragmentation leads to:

- Heterogeneous outcome domains, especially in clinical and physiological measures.
- Limited causal inference capacity, as the lack of Core Outcome Sets (COS) prevents robust cross-cohort synthesis.
- Inefficient data reuse, since harmonization with registries and trials is rarely achieved [8].

These gaps reflect a need for methodological services focused on standardization, including development of outcome frameworks and harmonization protocols.

Methodological Rigor in Causal Inference and IPD-MA Studies

Individual Participant Data Meta-Analyses (IPD-MAs) and causal inference studies face substantial methodological inconsistencies. Transparency is frequently limited, with incomplete reporting of missing data mechanisms, pooling assumptions, and harmonization procedures [47].

Key deficiencies include:

- Overreliance on singly robust models instead of doubly robust approaches for time-varying exposures [48].
- Lack of causal diagrams (DAGs) to clarify variable relationships.
- Limited use of hierarchical imputation preserving between-study heterogeneity [47].

- Weak or absent bias assessment frameworks beyond confounding (e.g., measurement error, selection bias) [47].

These deficiencies reduce reproducibility, comparability, and credibility of causal claims—underscoring the need for structured methodological services in causal reporting and transparency enhancement.

Integration between life sciences, environmental sciences and social sciences

Integration of social, environmental, behavioral, and biological information is poorly developed within most cohort infrastructures. Existing systems tend to separate psychosocial and molecular data, and there are few standardized frameworks or metadata models to bridge these domains [49]. This limits the ability to analyze how social exposures (such as stress or socioeconomic conditions) influence omic outcomes. In addition, technical capacity to merge omics data with real-time behavioral, wearable, or ecological datasets is lacking [50]. Without such integration, researchers cannot model the complex interactions between environment, lifestyle, and biology that drive health trajectories. Addressing this gap will require interoperable data platforms and advanced data-fusion methods linking biospecimens, digital health information, and contextual exposure measures [49], [50]. Examples in COVID-19 and aging research showcase analogous challenges: key sociodemographic and environmental variables are often missing, limiting understanding of health inequities [3], [26].

4. GAPS IN BIOBANKING AND OMICS SERVICES

In the literature, several gaps related to biobanking and OMICS services were identified.

Diversity, Representation, and Inclusion

Lack of diversity remains a fundamental weakness in biobanking and omics-based cohort studies. Many biobanks continue to underrepresent non-European ancestry groups, certain geographic regions, and a variety of tissue types, limiting the generalizability of findings and perpetuating health inequities [49], [51], [52].

Similarly, marginalized and understudied populations are often excluded from sampling frameworks, which further entrenches biases in data-driven research and clinical translation [33], [50]. To improve representativeness, cohorts require culturally sensitive consent processes, multilingual communication, and mobile or community-based sampling approaches that reach historically underrepresented groups.

Infrastructure, Sustainability, and Funding

The sustainability of omics repositories and cohort infrastructures is fragile. Several epigenomic databases have already ceased operations due to unstable funding, which disrupts data access and undermines reproducibility [49].

High operational costs and the resource intensity of multi-omics studies exacerbate this vulnerability. Integrative omics research requires substantial investment in specialized

instrumentation, informatics infrastructure, and interdisciplinary expertise that many cohorts cannot sustain [50].

Short-term grant cycles and limited funding mechanisms further undermine infrastructure continuity [49]. To ensure stability, cohorts need renewable funding models, shared governance structures, and national or international consortia capable of maintaining long-term data stewardship.

Methodological challenges in OMICS analysis

Across omics domains, methodological fragmentation limits data reliability and comparability. In epigenomics, reproducibility is hindered by variation in tissue selection, limited assay coverage, and cell composition effects [53]. Analytical approaches that can integrate multiple omic layers and demonstrate causality are still immature. Similarly, metabolomics faces major reproducibility challenges due to differences in instrumentation, analytical pipelines, and confounding influences such as diet or ethnicity [54]. Few multicenter validation studies exist to confirm metabolomics-based biomarkers, and the field lacks harmonized inter-laboratory protocols and quality-control standards [54]. Multi-omics studies as a whole suffer from an absence of standardized workflows for data normalization, quality control, and analysis [50].

Most omics datasets remain cross-sectional, providing only a single snapshot of molecular profiles. This severely limits causal inference and the ability to study biological change across the lifespan [50], [55]. Very few exposome or cancer-related cohort studies have implemented repeated sampling or long-term exposure tracking, despite the critical importance of such data for understanding disease progression. Additionally, many studies are statistically underpowered because sample sizes are too small to detect subtle genetic or multi-omic effects [50]. This leads to unstable associations and replication failures.

The translation of omics data into clinical or population-level applications is slowed by manual and fragmented analytical workflows [54]. There are few automated systems capable of handling the volume and complexity of omics data at scale. Incorporating machine learning-based quality control and diagnostic algorithms within cohort infrastructures could improve throughput, reproducibility, and translational utility.

Exposome-Specific Limitations

Research on the exposome—the cumulative environmental and chemical exposures influencing health—remains methodologically underdeveloped. Statistical methods and analytical pipelines lack harmonization, and there is no consensus on how to integrate exposome data with omics or epidemiological measures [55].

Existing exposome biobanks are limited in number and scale, and many lack long-term funding or standardized workflows for sample collection, processing, and data annotation [55]. Furthermore, a significant proportion of detected chemical signatures remain uncharacterized, leaving a “dark matter” component of the exposome that hinders mechanistic understanding [55]. Addressing these limitations requires improved cheminformatic algorithms, open-access annotation databases, and harmonized

international standards to enable data comparability and longitudinal analysis.

5. GAPS IN OPERATIONAL SUPPORT AND COORDINATION SERVICES

In the literature, several gaps related to operational support and coordination services were identified.

Inadequate Coordination of Recruitment and Retention Strategies

Recruitment and retention of participants are fragmented and dependent on individual study teams, with no overarching coordination or shared operational models. Literature reports that in birth cohorts, success in recruitment depended heavily on *individual efforts* (e.g., local clinics, cultural matching, or ad hoc incentives) [56]. There's no central support system to standardize or coordinate recruitment strategies across studies or to share best practices between teams. Similar issues appear in pre-dementia [57], [58] and advanced cancer studies [59], where recruitment bottlenecks arise from uncoordinated procedures, gatekeeping by clinicians, and lack of dedicated recruitment infrastructure. Operational support could provide shared recruitment toolkits, centralized participant registries, and training for recruiters (e.g., "research navigators" or "study liaisons"). It could also enable cross-cohort recruitment coordination (e.g., referring participants between related studies).

Missing Frameworks for Return of Results to Participants

There is no operational mechanism or dedicated support structure for ethically and efficiently returning research results to participants. The literature highlights that *sharing research results* is rarely planned or resourced within cohort operations [60]. This absence reduces participant trust and engagement, weakening long-term retention and societal impact. Cohorts lack guidance on designing communication materials, managing incidental findings, or allocating resources for feedback. A coordination service should establish standardized policies, templates, and ethical guidelines for returning results, ensuring proper staffing and communication planning from the design phase.

Lack of Strategic Coordination for Underrepresented Regions and Populations

There is a structural absence of operational frameworks to support cohort development in underrepresented regions or populations. Literature reports *insufficient research infrastructure* and *limited capacities* in Central and Eastern Europe for cognitive and aging research [61]. Similarly, recruitment barriers in advanced cancer and pregnancy cohorts point to inequitable inclusion (minorities, terminal patients, low-resource settings) [56] [59]. No coordination service exists to promote inclusivity or equitable resource distribution. Operational coordination services could focus on capacity building, regional partnerships, and inclusion strategies — helping underrepresented centers establish standardized, interoperable cohort infrastructures.

Workforce Limitations and Misalignment Between Clinical and Research Operations

Cohorts face persistent challenges due to uncoordinated staffing models and weak integration between clinical care and research logistics. Workforce shortages, limited staff availability, and siloed operations lead to missed recruitment opportunities and operational inefficiencies. Many studies cite the unavailability of research staff and restricted working hours as key barriers to recruitment and follow-up [57]. Recruitment and data management often rely on already overburdened clinical personnel rather than on a dedicated operational support unit. The absence of a coordinated staffing framework means that specialized personnel (e.g., data managers, research nurses, ethics coordinators) cannot be efficiently allocated or shared across studies. In advanced cancer cohorts, many eligible patients were never approached because clinical and research teams were not synchronized, highlighting the disconnection between care delivery and research processes [57]. Overall, cohort operations tend to function in silos, without seamless alignment with clinical workflows, electronic health record (EHR) systems, or patient scheduling.

SERVICE USER NEEDS IN THE LITERATURE

The literature reports also needs expressed by different stakeholders (e.g., researchers, patients and citizens, regulators, funders and policymakers).

Researchers

- **Data Access, Findability, and Metadata**

One of the most prominent needs among researchers is for findable and harmonized data infrastructures. Many studies emphasize the difficulty of identifying what cohort data exist, how they were collected, and under what conditions they can be reused [62] [5] [11]. Researchers therefore call for comprehensive metadata catalogues, detailed variable-level documentation, and clear information on data provenance.

Access mechanisms are also a point of concern. Transparent, standardized data access procedures and cost structures are essential to ensure equitable use of public resources [11]. Researchers highlight the value of centralized repositories for biobanks, molecular profiling, and real-world evidence datasets, particularly for rare diseases [63]. To enable collaboration while protecting privacy, there is a growing interest in federated analysis infrastructures such as DataSHIELD and Opal, which allow researchers to perform distributed analyses without physically sharing individual-level data [64] [12].

The transition toward FAIR-aligned (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) infrastructures is widely supported, as it facilitates not only access but also reproducibility and cross-study integration [64] [11].

- **Technical and Analytical Capacity**

Cohort research has become increasingly complex, requiring advanced analytical and computational skills. Researchers frequently identify the need for training and support in advanced statistics, causal inference, and bias correction methods applicable to observational and real-world data [45], [62], [65].

At the same time, technical assistance is needed to manage the challenges of data harmonization, cleaning, and transformation—tasks that are time-consuming but essential for multi-cohort analyses [5], [10]. The rapid expansion of multi-omics data and large-scale

computational infrastructures introduces further needs for training in data integration, storage, and high-performance analytics [50], [66].

Federated infrastructures, while promising, require specific technical expertise and user support to operate effectively [10], [11], [64]. As datasets grow in size and heterogeneity, researchers also require access to robust computational resources and standardized pipelines to manage big data, artificial intelligence, and exposome analyses [22], [54], [55].

- **Support with Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI)**

The increasing use of sensitive and cross-border data raises important ethical and legal challenges. Researchers consistently report uncertainty about how to navigate variations in national ethical standards and data protection laws, particularly under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [5], [27], [29].

They call for harmonized ethical frameworks that provide clear, consistent guidance on issues such as consent renewal, data reuse, participant recontact, and secondary use of health data [5], [30], [67]. Transparent governance mechanisms are also required to clarify questions of data ownership, accountability, and participant rights [5], [30].

In addition, ethical guidance is needed to avoid undue influence in contexts where clinical or institutional authority may compromise voluntary participation—for example, in mental health settings [67]. Researchers thus need institutional clarity and support in implementing ELSI-compliant practices across jurisdictions.

- **Collaboration and Communication Support**

Cohort research is inherently collaborative and depends on effective communication across multiple teams and institutions. Researchers highlight the need for continuous dialogue between data custodians and scientific users to ensure mutual understanding of data characteristics and research goals [5], [62].

Many point to the absence of responsive support systems capable of assisting with data access, troubleshooting, and project design. Establishing dedicated coordination teams and digital platforms for researcher interaction can significantly improve research efficiency and quality [10], [11], [64].

Such communication structures also play a key role in building trust between cohorts, enabling joint problem-solving, and fostering a culture of shared learning across consortia.

- **Sustainable Infrastructure and Governance**

Researchers stress the importance of long-term sustainability in cohort infrastructure and governance. Stable funding mechanisms are needed to maintain datasets, documentation, and access systems over time [10], [52]. Reproducibility depends on transparent reporting of data harmonization and analytical workflows [10], [68].

Standardized operating procedures and reproducible data pipelines are considered essential for ensuring the comparability of results across studies and countries [12], [64]. In addition, researchers call for governance models that balance centralized coordination with local autonomy, ensuring both efficiency and accountability [10], [12], [64].

- **Policy and Dissemination Skills**

Finally, researchers note a gap between cohort research and its policy impact. There is a clear need for training in research dissemination and policy translation, enabling scientists to communicate findings effectively to policymakers and the public [62].

At the same time, the academic reward system should better recognize the contributions of researchers who develop infrastructure, share data, or engage in interdisciplinary collaboration. New formats such as narrative CVs and contributorship models can help capture these forms of impact beyond traditional publication metrics [68], [69].

Patients / Citizens

- **Informed Consent and Autonomy**

Traditional static consent forms are no longer sufficient for long-term and evolving research contexts. Participants express a strong preference for dynamic consent mechanisms that allow them to stay informed about how their data are used and to modify their permissions over time [29], [30], [32].

They expect consent materials to be clear, concise, and comprehensible, avoiding technical jargon and using multimedia formats—such as videos, animations, or illustrated guides—to facilitate understanding [28], [30], [70]. Accessibility features are particularly important for older adults and those with limited literacy or digital skills [32], [70].

Moreover, participants value personal communication with study staff, which fosters trust and provides reassurance about data use and privacy [28]. For many, relational ethics—based on mutual respect and human connection—are as important as formal compliance mechanisms [70].

- **Communication of Results and Feedback**

Participants consistently express a desire for timely, transparent communication of research outcomes. They view receiving study results—whether individual or aggregate—as part of their right to information and recognition of their contribution [60], [71].

They prefer that results be communicated in accessible, lay-friendly language, and through preferred channels such as email updates, printed newsletters, or online dashboards [60], [72].

Providing feedback even when results are negative or inconclusive helps maintain trust and demonstrates accountability [60].

Such communication should be timely, ideally occurring close to publication or at key milestones in the study [60], [72]. Personalized feedback systems, where possible, strengthen engagement and participant satisfaction.

- **Accessibility and Inclusion**

Barriers to participation remain widespread, particularly for people with disabilities, linguistic minorities, and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups. Participants call for culturally adapted recruitment and communication strategies, as well as multilingual and accessible materials that reflect the diversity of potential cohorts [32], [73], [74].

Reducing participant burden is also key. Flexible participation modes—such as online surveys, home-based sampling, or hybrid designs—make participation feasible for a wider range of individuals [41], [50]. Additionally, participants with disabilities emphasize the need for systems that support autonomy and reduce dependence on gatekeepers in healthcare or social institutions [75].

- **Empowerment and Co-Production**

Participants increasingly expect to have an active voice in how cohort studies are governed and conducted. Many advocate for co-production models in which participants contribute feedback, suggest research topics, or help shape data governance frameworks [29], [38], [72].

Digital consent tools enable this by providing platforms for two-way communication and real-time decision-making [29], [30]. Such participatory approaches not only enhance ethical legitimacy but also improve data quality and retention by aligning research more closely with participants' values and expectations.

Regulators / Funders / Policymakers

- **Evaluation and Incentive Reform**

Traditional research evaluation systems remain poorly suited to recognizing collaborative, infrastructural, and open-science contributions. Funders increasingly support narrative CVs and contributorship models that reward data sharing, training, and cross-sector collaboration [68], [69].

There is also a growing interest in machine-readable indicators of openness and data sharing to integrate such practices into funding assessments [69]. By shifting incentives, policymakers hope to normalize transparency and cooperation as integral aspects of scientific excellence.

- **Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI)**

Ensuring that cohort research reflects social and biological diversity is a major policy goal. Regulators highlight the need for inclusive recruitment, representation of underrepresented populations, and diverse research teams [48], [49], [55], [76].

Policies should also support interdisciplinary training that bridges social and data sciences, thereby preventing algorithmic bias and ensuring equitable AI applications in health [20], [48], [49]. Regulatory frameworks must similarly promote transparency in how algorithms are developed and validated [20], [48].

CONSOLIDATED GAP ANALYSIS

The consolidated gap analysis has been informed by surveys and interviews with infrastructure service providers (Task 4.1), semi-structured interviews with service users (Task 4.2), the scoping literature review presented in the previous chapter (Task 4.3) and a stakeholder consultation workshop with 30 cohort experts that took place on 14 November 2025 and allowed us to validate, extend and prioritise the identified gaps.

1. DATA SERVICES

Presentation of gaps

Table 2 Identified gaps in the provision of data services

1 Gaps in Data services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
1.1	Data Standardization, Harmonization, and Interoperability	Inconsistent use of data standards and vocabularies across regions, organizations, and data types leads to poor interoperability and fragmented datasets. Limited adoption of standards such as CDISC, OMOP, HL7 FHIR, and DICOM, along with terminological inconsistencies and lack of harmonisation, hinder data integration, comparability, and large-scale sharing.
1.2	Data Completeness and Data Quality	Lack of standardized, continuous, and quality-controlled data collection in cohorts using real-world data (RWD). Fragmented health information systems and the absence of routine validation processes result in missing or inconsistent records. These issues reduce data reliability and introduce biases.
1.3	Design of Case Report Forms and Implementation of Automated Data Capture	Limited support for the design and implementation of CRFs and automated data capture instruments. The lack of automated metadata annotation leads to persistent manual processes and reduced efficiency in managing cohort data.
1.4	Individual Participant Data Linkage and Integration Across Different Health Databases	Linking individual patient data across sources is essential but poorly implemented, with many systems lacking robust identity linkage or tokenization. Privacy-preserving integration infrastructure is fragmented and inconsistent across countries.
1.5	AI and ML: Computational Infrastructure, Robustness and Generalizability of the Algorithms	Computational infrastructure for large-scale AI and ML research is often inadequate; with many institutions lacking the hardware and scalable environments needed for advanced models. Limited, biased, or unrepresentative datasets reduce generalisability and reproducibility, while small, labelled datasets, lack of diversity, and insufficient validation hinder trustworthy AI-driven analyses in clinical and imaging research.
1.6	Privacy-Preserving Methods, Secure Data Analysis Platforms and Federated Networks	Challenges with defining data anonymisation/pseudonymisation methods that balance data utility with confidentiality. Few Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) available. Need for the establishment of a collaborative federated analytics network.
1.7	(Cohort) Data Discoverability, Metadata Availability and Quality	Cohort registration is not mandatory, making it difficult to know which studies are active, where they are conducted, and what data they collect. Many datasets also lack standardized metadata, persistent identifiers, and cataloguing, reducing findability and reuse. Promoting the adoption of metadata standards and implementing

1 Gaps in Data services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
		harmonized frameworks—such as those supported by the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and Health-DCAT-AP—are essential to improve consistency, interoperability, and enable large-scale, cross-cohort research.
1.8	Availability of European Cloud Providers and Computational Platforms	Currently, cloud resources for big-data collaborations are mainly provided by non-EU cloud providers raising concerns about data sovereignty, governance, and alignment with EU values.

Gap prioritization: Data services

Gap prioritization was conducted by the workshop participants using Microsoft Forms, and the results are presented in Figure 4 as a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart showing the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 4 Ranking of gaps in Cluster 1: Data services

Top priorities:

Data Standardization, Harmonization, and Interoperability (Rank 1) and *(Cohort) Data Discoverability, Metadata Availability and Quality* (Rank 2) are most frequently chosen as top priorities, as indicated by the large dark brown and medium brown sections.

Moderate priorities:

Data Completeness and Data Quality (Rank 3) and *Privacy-Preserving Methods, Secure Data Analysis Platforms and Federated Networks* (Rank 4) have a more even distribution across high and mid-level rankings, suggesting participants see them as important but less urgent than the top two.

Mixed priorities:

Some gaps, such as *Individual Participant Data Linkage and Integration Across Different Health Databases* (Rank 5) and *Design of Case Report Forms and Implementation of Automated Data Capture* (Rank 6), show a broad spread across the ranking spectrum, suggesting varying views among participants about their importance.

Lower priorities:

Availability of European Cloud Providers and Computational Platforms (Rank 7) and *AI and ML: Computational Infrastructure, Robustness and Generalizability of the Algorithms* (Rank 8) show large sections in light and dark blue, indicating these were often ranked as lower priorities.

2. REGULATORY AND ETHICAL SUPPORT SERVICES

Presentation of gaps

Table 3 Identified gaps in the provision of regulatory and ethical support services

2 Gaps in Regulatory and Ethical Support services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
2.1	Institutional Capacity for Ethical, Legal and Regulatory Support	Limited institutional capacity to provide ELSI expertise for cohort data transfer and reuse, particularly in cross-border and international research collaborations. Intellectual property issues also pose challenges for engaging in industry partnerships.
2.2	Inconsistent ELSI Requirements Across Jurisdictions	Researchers face challenges due to varying ethical, legal, and social standards between countries (e.g., GDPR inconsistent implementation). Differences in data protection, consent, and governance rules complicate cross-border data sharing and collaboration, creating uncertainty and administrative burdens.
2.3	Deficiencies in Informed Consent Models and Implementation	Traditional one-time consent forms are often unclear, inconsistent, and inadequate for long-term, evolving research. Poorly designed forms can hinder data sharing and make re-consenting time-consuming, while participants increasingly favor dynamic consent mechanisms that keep them informed, allow them to adjust permissions, and provide materials in clear, online, and multimedia formats. It is essential that ethics committees receive comprehensive guidance to effectively evaluate digital consent tools.
2.4	Emerging Ethical, Legal and Regulatory Gaps from AI and Digital Health Technologies	Challenges exist in ensuring responsible and compliant AI use in research and healthcare. Although the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) establishes a risk-based framework to safeguard rights, its implications for cohort-based AI—especially for data-sharing and anonymisation—remain unclear. Algorithmic bias, limited safety validation, and unclear accountability further underscore the need for clear guidance and robust governance.

Gap prioritization: Regulatory and Ethical Support services

Gap prioritization was conducted by the workshop participants using Microsoft Forms, and the results are presented in Figure 5 as a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart showing the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 5 Ranking of gaps in Cluster 2: Regulatory and Ethical Support services

Top priority:

Inconsistent ELSI Requirements Across Jurisdictions (Rank 1) clearly emerges as the top priority, as it received the strongest concentration of first-choice rankings, indicating broad consensus on the urgency of cross-jurisdictional harmonisation.

Moderate priorities:

Deficiencies in Informed Consent Models and Implementation (Rank 2) and *Institutional Capacity for Ethical, Legal and Regulatory Support* (Rank 3) fall into the category of moderate priorities; both are consistently ranked among the upper and mid-level positions, reflecting their importance, particularly in evolving digital and cross-border research contexts, though they are seen as less urgent than addressing cross-jurisdictional inconsistency.

Lower priority:

Emerging Ethical, Legal and Regulatory Gaps from AI and Digital Health Technologies (Rank 4) is classified as a lower priority, as it is most frequently ranked among the later choices, suggesting that it is perceived as an important but longer-term or emerging concern rather than an immediate service gap.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN SERVICES

Presentation of gaps

Table 4 Identified gaps in the provision of methodology and design se

3 Gaps in Methodology and Design services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
3.1	Protocol Registration and Feasibility Assessment	Limited practice and service provision for registering study protocols and systematically evaluating the feasibility of proposed research. Without protocol registration, it is difficult to track ongoing studies, prevent duplication, and ensure transparency. Inadequate feasibility assessment—such as estimating participant availability, data completeness, or resource needs—can lead to inefficient study designs and recruitment challenges.
3.2	Harmonised Processes and Tools	Lack of standardized methods, workflows, and tools across studies limits efficiency, comparability, and collaboration. Variations in data collection, analysis, and quality control, along with inconsistent Core Outcome Sets (COS), create heterogeneous outcomes that hinder cross-cohort integration and robust causal inference.
3.3	Limited integration of Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) in study designs	Involvement of participants and advocacy groups in cohort research is often tokenistic. PPI is usually confined to early stages like study design or data collection and rarely informs governance or strategic decision-making. Barriers include limited resources, lack of funder awareness about PPI needs, unclear communication, and researcher skepticism. Digital tools can enhance engagement, but efforts must be inclusive and sensitive to cultural, linguistic, and literacy differences to ensure equitable participation.
3.4	Disentangling Correlated Temporal Factors: Age, Cohort, and Time Period in Multivariate or Longitudinal Analyses	In multivariate or longitudinal studies, the effects of a person's chronological age, their birth cohort, and the period when data are collected are often intertwined. This correlation makes it difficult to determine whether observed differences are due to aging itself, generational characteristics, or time-specific influences such as social or historical events. Failing to separate these factors can lead to ambiguous or misleading conclusions, limiting the interpretability and reliability of study findings.
3.5	Methodological Transparency and Robustness in Causal Analyses	Lack of clear reporting and rigorous methods in cohort studies limits causal inference. Key issues include incomplete documentation of missing data, pooling assumptions, and harmonization procedures, overreliance on singly robust models, limited use of causal diagrams (DAGs), and insufficient bias assessment beyond confounding. Standardized use of robust methods—such as propensity scores, inverse probability weighting, matching, hierarchical imputation, and quantitative bias analyses—could enhance credibility.
3.6	Control of Confounding in Observational and Cohort Studies	Challenge of addressing both measured and unmeasured variables that can bias causal inference. Many studies inconsistently apply standard methods such as multivariate regression, stratification, or propensity score matching, and often fail to adjust for key demographic, clinical, or

3 Gaps in Methodology and Design services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
		socioeconomic covariates. Residual confounding from unmeasured factors further undermines validity, while over-restriction or underpowered stratified analyses can limit generalizability. Adopting formal causal inference frameworks—such as target trial emulation, g-methods, and advanced longitudinal estimators—can improve adjustment for confounding.
3.7	Integration between Biological, Social and Environmental Factors	Limited ability of cohort studies to combine diverse data types across disciplines. Biological, social, and environmental information is often collected and stored separately, with few standardized frameworks or metadata models to link them. This fragmentation, combined with insufficient technical and analytical tools, hinders the study of how interactions between genetics, lifestyle, and environmental exposures shape health and aging trajectories.

Gap prioritization: Methodology and Design services

Gap prioritization was conducted by the workshop participants using Microsoft Forms, and the results are presented in Figure 6 as a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart showing the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 6 Ranking of gaps in Cluster 3: Methodology and Design services

Top priorities:

Harmonised Processes and Tools (Rank 1) and *Protocol Registration and Feasibility Assessment* (Rank 2) were clearly identified as the highest priorities. Both topics received a strong concentration of first- and second-choice rankings, indicating a high level of agreement among participants on their urgency and foundational importance for improving

current practice.

Moderate priorities:

Methodological Transparency and Robustness in Causal Analyses (Rank 3) and the *Limited Integration of Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) in Study Designs* (Rank 4) were positioned in the middle of the ranking. These areas were consistently viewed as important, but the wider spread of votes suggests less consensus on their immediate priority compared with the top-ranked gaps.

Mixed priority:

Disentangling Correlated Temporal Factors: Age, Cohort, and Time Period in Multivariate or Longitudinal Analyses (Rank 5) showed a mixed pattern of prioritisation. The distribution of votes across mid and lower ranks indicates divergent views among participants, likely reflecting differences in methodological focus and practical relevance across disciplines.

Lower priorities:

Integration between Biological, Social and Environmental Factors (Rank 6) and *Control of Confounding in Observational and Cohort Studies* (Rank 7) were most frequently ranked toward the lower end of the priority scale. While still recognised as relevant methodological challenges, these areas were perceived as less urgent relative to the other identified service gaps.

4. BIOBANKING AND OMICS SERVICES

Presentation of gaps

Table 5 Identified gaps in the provision of biobanking and omics services

4 Gaps in Biobanking and OMICS services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
4.1	Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in Biobanking and OMICS	Lack of consistent, standardized practices for handling, processing, and analyzing biosamples and omics data across cohorts. Many studies operate with ad hoc workflows, limited SOPs, and variable metadata quality, while few multicenter validations exist to confirm biomarkers. This inconsistency undermines reproducibility, comparability, and cross-cohort integration. Closing this gap requires implementing harmonized SOPs, ISO-compliant standards, certified service providers, shared data dictionaries, reference materials, and robust QA/QC frameworks to ensure reliable, interoperable, and high-quality biobanking and multi-omics research.
4.2	Inclusion of Biobanking and OMICS Analysis in Cohort Studies	Limited incorporation of biological sample collection and molecular profiling into cohort infrastructures. Many studies lack the resources, expertise, and infrastructure needed to support high-quality biobanking, repeated sampling, and comprehensive OMICS analyses. This limits the ability to link biological mechanisms with environmental and lifestyle

4 Gaps in Biobanking and OMICS services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
		factors over time.
4.3	Diversity and Representation in Biobanks and OMICS Databases	Lack of diversity remains a major limitation in biobanking and omics-based cohort studies. Non-European ancestry groups, underrepresented regions, and diverse tissue types are often missing, reducing generalizability and reinforcing health inequities. Exclusion of marginalized populations further entrenches bias in data-driven research and clinical translation.
4.4	Harmonisation in Biobanking and OMICS Methods and Analysis	Harmonisation in biobanking and omics methods and analysis is limited by inconsistent protocols for sample collection, processing, and data analysis. In epigenomics, variability in tissue selection and assay coverage affects reproducibility, while in metabolomics, differences in instrumentation, analytical pipelines, and confounding factors such as diet or ethnicity further reduce comparability. Multi-omics studies also face assay variability, high costs, and a lack of standardized validation procedures, underscoring the need for unified quality-control and methodological frameworks.
4.5	Exposome Specific Limitations	Methodological and infrastructural gaps hinder comprehensive assessment of environmental and chemical exposures over time. These include fragmented analytical methods, limited integration with omics and epidemiological data, insufficiently standardized biobanking workflows, and a large proportion of uncharacterized chemical signatures, leaving much of the exposome's biological impact poorly understood.
4.6	Infrastructure Sustainability and Scalability	High operational costs, resource-intensive multi-omics workflows, and short-term grant cycles lead to interrupted services and even closure of key databases. Manual, fragmented analytical pipelines and lack of automated, scalable systems (for storage, compute, QC and data curation) slow translation and reduce reproducibility.

Gap prioritization: Biobanking and OMICS services

Gap prioritization was conducted by the workshop participants using Microsoft Forms, and the results are presented in Figure 7 as a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart showing the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 7 Ranking of gaps in Cluster 4: Biobanking and OMICS services

Top priorities:

Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in Biobanking and OMICS (Rank 1) emerges as the strongest top priority. It has the highest proportion of first-choice and high-ranking selections, showing strong and consistent support across respondents. *Inclusion of Biobanking and OMICS Analysis in Cohort Studies* (Rank 2) is also a clear top priority, with many respondents ranking it first or second.

Moderate priority:

Harmonisation in Biobanking and OMICS Methods and Analysis (Rank 3) falls within the moderate priority range. It is consistently ranked in the middle to upper-middle positions, reflecting broad recognition of its relevance. This pattern suggests that while stakeholders generally agree on its importance, it is often prioritised below issues related to quality, inclusion, and broader harmonisation in biobanking and OMICS analyses.

Mixed priority:

Infrastructure Sustainability and Scalability (Rank 4) shows some mixed behavior—while often ranked lower, it still receives a noticeable share of mid-level rankings, suggesting it may be seen as important but less urgent compared to core methodological issues.

Lower priorities:

Diversity and Representation in Biobanks and OMICS Databases (Rank 5) is generally ranked lower, with most responses clustering toward the last choices. *Exposome-Specific Limitations* (Rank 6) is the lowest overall priority, with the majority of respondents placing it at the very bottom.

5. OPERATIONAL SUPPORT AND COORDINATION SERVICES

Presentation of gaps

Table 6 Identified gaps in the provision of operational support and coordination services

5 Gaps in Operational Support and Coordination services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
5.1	Inadequate Participant Recruitment and Retention Strategies	Limited capacity of cohort infrastructures to systematically recruit and retain participants. Recruitment often relies on ad hoc, site-specific efforts, with no centralized systems to coordinate strategies or share best practices. Bottlenecks arise from uncoordinated procedures, clinician gatekeeping, and limited outreach infrastructure, while long-term participant engagement is hampered by insufficient support and motivation strategies.
5.2	Scarcity of Service Providers that Offer Operational Support for Cohort Studies	Limited availability of organizations that can assist with key operational aspects of cohort research. While some cohorts access private companies or public/university-based services for study planning, design, proposal writing, surveys, or data collection, such support is not widely available or standardized.
5.3	Difficulties with Administrative Processes for Data Access and Lack of Transparency in Cost-Recovery Models	Opaque funding and fee systems — ranging from core-funded services to project-based support or per-use charges — hinder equitable, predictable access to cohort data and infrastructure. Cumbersome, time-consuming data-access requests, long procurement cycles, and weak administrative capacity create both operational and financial barriers. Greater transparency in cost-recovery, clear access frameworks, practical help desks, and stronger administrative support are needed.
5.4	Workforce Limitations and Misalignment between Clinical and Research Operations	Staff shortages and funding constraints leave cohorts without the specialized personnel they need—bioinformaticians, data engineers, data managers, research nurses, and ethics coordinators—to manage complex data and sensitive workflows. Recruitment, follow-up, and data management frequently fall on overburdened clinical staff with limited time, rather than on dedicated operational teams, causing delays, reduced data quality, and missed opportunities for efficient sharing of expertise across studies.
5.5	Missing Frameworks for Return of Results to Research Participants	Cohorts often lack guidance on designing participant-friendly communication materials, managing incidental findings, and allocating resources to provide timely feedback. Participants value receiving both individual and aggregate results in clear, accessible formats through preferred channels, viewing this as recognition of their contribution and a right to information.
5.6	Lack of Strategic Coordination for Underrepresented Regions and Populations	Absence of EU-level strategies and uneven infrastructure (notably in Central and Eastern Europe) that leave cohorts under-resourced and participant samples unrepresentative. Cultural, linguistic, digital, logistical and trust barriers systematically exclude minorities, low-income, rural, disabled and non-native language groups. Coordinated, participatory approaches—community/bilingual staff, translated materials, co-designed recruitment, and targeted

5 Gaps in Operational Support and Coordination services		
	Gap Title	Integrated Gaps (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
		funding—are needed to improve inclusion, reduce bias, and ensure equitable research benefits.
5.7	Limited User Support and Navigation Tools for Cohort collaborations	Lack of accessible, user-friendly systems to guide researchers through cohort operational processes. Users report a need for tools that simplify data access, troubleshooting, and project planning, while fostering clear communication between data custodians and scientific users.

Gap prioritization: Operational Support and Coordination services

Gap prioritization was conducted by the workshop participants using Microsoft Forms, and the results are presented in Figure 8 as a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart showing the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 8 Ranking of gaps in Cluster 5: Operational Support and Coordination services

Top priorities:

Inadequate Participant Recruitment and Retention Strategies (Rank 1) is the top priority, with the highest concentration of first-choice rankings, indicating it is viewed as the most urgent operational challenge. *Workforce Limitations and Misalignment between Clinical and Research Operations* (Rank 2) also ranks very highly, with many first- and second-choice selections, underscoring major concerns about staffing capacity and coordination.

Moderate priorities:

Scarcity of Service Providers that Offer Operational Support for Cohort Studies (Rank 3) and *Difficulties with Administrative Processes for Data Access and Lack of Transparency in Cost-Recovery Models* (Rank 4) fall into the moderate priority range. These issues receive a mix of high and mid-level rankings, suggesting they are important and widely felt, but not as critical as recruitment or workforce challenges.

Mixed priorities:

Difficulties with Administrative Processes for Data Access and Cost-Recovery Transparency (Rank 4) shows some mixed behavior, with notable support in both mid and lower ranks, suggesting it is perceived as a significant barrier in some contexts but not universally urgent.

Lower priorities:

Missing Frameworks for Return of Results to Research Participants (Rank 5), *Lack of Strategic Coordination for Underrepresented Regions and Populations* (Rank 6), and *Limited User Support and Navigation Tools for Cohort Collaborations* (Rank 7) are generally ranked toward the lower end. These topics receive a high proportion of last-choice rankings, indicating they are seen as less immediate or less pressing compared to core operational barriers.

CROSS-CUTTING ISSUES

Cross-cutting gaps refer to overarching, systemic issues—such as sustainability, coordination, visibility, evaluation, and training—that affect the provision and quality of services for large medical cohorts across all service clusters.

Table 7 Identified cross-cutting issues affecting service provision across all clusters

Cross-cutting issues	
Title	Integrated cross-cutting issue (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
Sustainability	Lack of stable, long-term funding and investment needed to maintain infrastructure, governance, and essential services. Cohort and longitudinal studies require predictable financing to support data collection, biobanking, metadata curation, and access systems, as well as to retain skilled personnel. Uncertainty in budgets, particularly over extended preparatory and operational phases, threatens service continuity, data quality, and the overall viability of large-scale research efforts.
Lack of Visibility, Coordination and Scalability in Service Provision	While a variety of services exist across Europe, they are often confined to individual organizations or collaborations, with little coordination or scaling across the broader cohort community. Researchers highlight the need for clearer overviews of available services, better alignment with user needs, and mechanisms to repurpose existing infrastructure.
Limited Integration of Data Sharing Criteria in Research Evaluation and Funding Systems	Traditional academic rewards favour publications over infrastructure contributions, data curation, or collaboration, discouraging open data practices. Intellectual property, competition, and reputational concerns further limit sharing. Addressing this requires clear incentives—such as data citations, FAIR assessments, and contributor recognition (e.g., CRediT)—integrated into funding and publication evaluations to promote transparency, collaboration, and maximize the scientific and societal value of cohort investments.

Cross-cutting issues	
Title	Integrated cross-cutting issue (Service Provision, User Needs and Scoping Literature Review)
Training	<p>Need to develop a workforce capable of managing complex studies and data. Key areas include data stewardship and metadata management, bioinformatics and multi-omics analyses, advanced biostatistics and methodology, and legal and ethical compliance, with attention to diversity and fairness. Clinicians and researchers also need training in ML, NLP, and AI methods, and technical skills for data harmonization, cleaning, transformation, and integration for multi-cohort analyses.</p> <p>Operational skills—such as project coordination, cohort management, and roles like data curators and legal advisors—are also essential. Limited in-house capacity increases reliance on costly external support, emphasizing the need for accessible, structured training programs, ideally supported at the EU level, to strengthen expertise, reproducibility, and the effective use of complex datasets and computational infrastructures.</p>

WORKSHOP EXPERT INSIGHTS: KEY GAPS AND MISSING SERVICES

The workshop participants were explicitly invited to identify additional gaps where existing services fall short of user needs. The findings below, organised by theme, summarise the key gaps that affect large medical cohort research in Europe, as highlighted by experts during the WP4 consultation workshop held on 14 November 2025.

Data, Cloud and Federated Services

Stakeholders highlighted technical and analytical gaps particularly in **AI/ML** capacities, **data discoverability**, **cloud infrastructures**, and **federated analytics**. Participants distinguished challenges using pre-trained AI/ML models, often reliant on proprietary, non-transparent, and non-EU systems, from training new models, which require large, diverse datasets and raise concerns about model leakage and legal or ethical concerns.

Data and cohort discoverability emerged as a critical and persistent structural gap, with existing catalogues providing insufficient visibility into cohorts and their variables.

While some participants noted that European cloud services technically exist, most emphasized low awareness, complex procurement pathways, limited certified environments for sensitive data, and institutional restrictions that push researchers to commercial, non-EU platforms. Federated analytics was broadly welcomed but regarded as still immature due to limited tooling, incomplete semantic alignment, and analytical tasks that cannot be performed within privacy-preserving frameworks.

Ethical, Legal and Societal Gaps and Regulatory Challenges

Stakeholders identified legal, ethical and governance support as a major unresolved gap, particularly where emerging research practices meet uneven regulatory interpretation. **Dynamic consent** was recognised as vital for longitudinal cohorts, yet its implementation impeded by regulatory uncertainty, divergent ethics committees decisions, and absent harmonised EU-level guidance.

Capacity gaps within Data Protection Officers and ethics committees—especially regarding AI-enabled research and digital health—often shift the burden of interpretation and compliance onto researchers. **Cross-border collaboration** faces heterogeneous regulatory requirements both across and within countries, cause delays and confusion around international data transfers. Experts called for a European ELSI network, EUREC-collaborated e-dynamic consent guidelines, clearer EU regulation alignment, AI expertise in ethics committees, harmonised shared templates, improved GDPR trainings and structured support for integrating data altruism and citizen-generated data, and greater clarity on **European Health Data Space**.

Methodology and Design

Methodological challenges spancohort design, harmonisation, and causal inference. **Feasibility assessment frameworks** exist, but stakeholders described them as fragmented, inconsistently applied, and specific to research communities.

Methodological issues that are manageable within a single cohort become substantially complex in multi-cohort or federated analyses due to heterogeneous missing data, opaque data-generating processes, and bias risks. **Attrition and missingness**—particularly in longitudinal studies—remain under-addressed sources of bias, while causal diagrams and models remain unevenly used across fields. **Trial emulation** was viewed as a valuable, though methodologically demanding tool for answering causal questions where randomised trials are not feasible, with adoption still limited and under debate.

Biobanking, OMICS and Quality Assurance Gaps

Quality assurance, omics integration, and biobanking challenges featured prominently in the discussion. Stakeholders emphasised pre-analytical phase of biosample handling—collection, timing, transport, and documentation—as most vulnerable, impacting downstream omics analyses.

Variability in sample collection across sites and countries, **high cost of omics technologies, fragmented datasets, and rapid technological evolution** all contribute to inconsistency, technical noise, and harmonisation barriers.

While biobanks enable coordinated workflows, participants noted that many emerging biobanks lack clear guidance on minimum omics requirements, standards for data provenance, and expectations for long-term cohort integration and storage. Experts called for EU-facilitated transnational access to next-generation genomic technologies and analysis centres alongside clearer omics standards.

Operational Support and Coordination

Operational challenges related to **cohort recruitment, retention, communication, and**

workforce sustainability were likewise widely reported. High population mobility, delayed loss to follow-up detection, and complex re-consent procedures (children transitioning to adulthood). **Patient and Public Involvement** is improving, but remains resource-intensive, communication with participants—especially returning study results—was seen as essential for maintaining trust but remains constrained by limited staffing and communication expertise. Workforce instability and high turnover, underline the need for stable, dedicated personnel.

Funding and Sustainability Gaps

Persistent structural funding gaps threaten the long-term sustainability of cohort research in Europe. Most cohorts rely on short-term, competitive grants that prioritise scientific novelty over the continuity of core operations (data management, participant follow-up, and maintenance of collaboration networks). Funders recognise these limitations but face programme duration, budget structures, and evaluation criteria that disadvantage the extension of existing cohorts. Participants highlighted that a national-EU misalignment persists, with European programmes assuming short-term project funding and national systems expected to support long-term infrastructure—yet neither providing adequate coverage. This mutual deferral creates a structural gap in sustainable funding at both levels.

TOP TEN PRIORITY GAPS ACROSS ALL SERVICE CLUSTERS

During the stakeholder consultation workshop we aimed to produce a consolidated top-ten list of priority gaps across all service clusters. A two-step ranking approach was applied. First, within each service cluster, the gaps that scored within the top 33% based on participants' initial rankings were shortlisted. These high-priority gaps from each cluster were then brought together into a single pool. In a second step, workshop participants took part in a final ranking exercise to prioritise these shortlisted gaps across clusters, resulting in an overall top-ten list of the most critical service gaps.

Figure 9 displays a ranked stacked horizontal bar chart with the distribution of priority votes across service gaps.

Figure 9 Top-ten ranking of higher-priority gaps across all service clusters

Top priorities:

Data Standardization, Harmonization, and Interoperability (Rank 1) clearly emerge as the highest priority, with a strong concentration of first- and second-choice rankings. *(Cohort) Data Discoverability, Metadata Availability and Quality* (Rank 2) and *Data Completeness and Data Quality* (Rank 3) are also top priorities, consistently ranked highly across respondents, highlighting the central importance of robust and harmonized data management.

Mixed and moderate priorities:

Inconsistent ELSI Requirements Across Jurisdictions (Rank 4) and *Harmonised Processes and Tools* (Rank 5) show some mixed rankings, reflecting that while they may not be the very top priorities, they are recognized as essential for enabling broader data interoperability and collaboration.

Lower priorities:

Inadequate Participant Recruitment and Retention Strategies (Rank 6), *Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in Biobanking and OMICS* (Rank 7), *Workforce Limitations and Misalignment between Clinical and Research Operations* (Rank 8), *Inclusion of Biobanking and OMICS Analysis in Cohort Studies* (Rank 9), and *Protocol Registration and Feasibility Assessment* (Rank 10) are generally ranked lower in this list, with a higher proportion of last-choice selections. These topics, while relevant operationally, are considered less urgent compared with the critical data-related challenges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This section aims to provide ten high-level recommendations based on the outcomes of the consolidated gap analysis and the prioritization exercise. These are addressed to policymakers and funders as well as researchers involved in cohort studies.

1) Ensure long-term financial sustainability of cohorts and supporting infrastructures.

Large medical cohorts generate their greatest value over decades, yet funding remains dominated by short-term, project-based cycles. Sustainable financing is essential to maintain continuous data collection, biobanking operations, metadata curation, technological upgrades, and the retention of trained personnel. Long-term investment frameworks—potentially combining EU-level programmes with embedding the cohorts within existing infrastructures whenever possible, national sources, and multi-stakeholder co-funding—are needed to prevent fragmentation, avoid interruptions in data quality, and enable stable multi-cohort collaboration.

2) Promote regulatory and ethical harmonisation across jurisdictions.

Cross-border research continues to face delays and uncertainty due to variable interpretations of GDPR, inconsistent ethics review processes, and divergent consent requirements. Developing harmonised templates for data access agreements, dynamic and electronic consent procedures, and governance structures for international data sharing will reduce administrative burden and enable smoother collaboration. Strengthening regulatory capacity—particularly among ethics committees and Data Protection Officers—will ensure consistent, high-quality decision-making aligned with evolving technologies and the European Health Data Space.

3) Advance data standardisation, interoperability, and metadata quality.

Heterogeneous data standards and incomplete metadata limit the usability of cohort data and hinder integration. A coordinated push toward shared terminologies, data models, and harmonised metadata frameworks is needed to enable efficient multi-cohort analysis. Requiring cohort registration and adopting FAIR-aligned findability practices can significantly improve discoverability, reduce duplication, and support reproducibility. Investments in automated metadata generation, persistent identifiers, and shared data dictionaries will further strengthen coherence across infrastructures.

4) Strengthen methodological rigor and transparency.

Cohort studies face substantial heterogeneity in design, outcome definitions, data harmonisation, and bias control. Routine use of feasibility assessments, protocol registration, and standardised workflows across design, analysis, and reporting can enhance comparability and reduce redundancy. Promoting robust causal-inference frameworks, transparent documentation of assumptions, and clear reporting of missing data and harmonisation processes will increase confidence in findings and support cross-cohort synthesis and reuse.

5) Expand capacity for federated and privacy-preserving data analysis.

Federated analytics are increasingly essential for cross-border research, yet current tools remain fragmented and technically demanding. Investments in EU-based, secure, user-

friendly federated platforms—together with clear legal guidance on privacy-preserving record linkage, tokenisation, and pseudonymisation—will support data utility while maintaining participant confidentiality. Establishing common standards for governance, access control, and quality assurance will help scale federated infrastructures from pilots to fully operational solutions.

6) Improve biobanking and multi-omics quality, harmonisation, and representativeness.

High-quality biosamples and omics data require strict pre-analytical and analytical standards. Implementing harmonised SOPs, ISO-compliant QA/QC systems, interoperable metadata standards, and multi-centre validation studies is necessary to enhance reproducibility across Europe. At the same time, cohorts must improve representation of diverse populations and tissue types to avoid perpetuating health inequities. Sustained investment in scalable, automated omics pipelines and interoperable data platforms will strengthen the integration of omics into cohort infrastructures.

7) Establish coordinated operational support structures for cohorts.

Many operational barriers—recruitment, retention, communication with participants, return-of-results processes, administrative support—are repeated across cohorts but solved locally. Creating shared operational service hubs, offering tools, templates, and trained personnel, would reduce inefficiency and strengthen overall quality. Centralised navigation support, helpdesks, or matchmaking platforms could improve researcher experience, accelerate access procedures, and support alignment with clinical workflows and participant needs.

8) Address workforce shortages and build multidisciplinary expertise.

Cohort research increasingly requires specialised roles—data stewards, bioinformaticians, statisticians, clinical research staff, ethics coordinators, and project managers—yet many institutions face shortages and high turnover. Supporting structured career pathways, long-term contracts, and cross-cohort staff-sharing mechanisms will improve continuity and efficiency. EU-wide training and certification programmes in data management, AI/ML, omics, ELSI compliance, and health-data governance can help harmonise skills and reduce capacity disparities between regions.

9) Promote inclusive, participant-centred research practices.

Equitable participation is essential for generalisable science and public trust. Developing multilingual, culturally adapted consent materials, accessible study information, community-based recruitment approaches, and options for dynamic consent will enhance inclusion and autonomy. Designing low-burden participation pathways—hybrid visits, remote data collection, flexible scheduling—can improve retention. Strengthening mechanisms for returning individual and aggregate results will help maintain engagement and reinforce participants' sense of contribution and recognition.

10) Reform incentive structures to reward open, collaborative, and infrastructure-oriented science.

Current evaluation systems undervalue data stewardship, harmonisation efforts, software development, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Incorporating open-science indicators, data citations, narrative CVs, and contributor frameworks into funding and assessment processes would align rewards with the work needed to sustain large cohorts. Encouraging

transparent, FAIR-aligned data sharing and recognising infrastructure contributions will maximise the scientific and societal returns on public investment.

OUTLOOK

The WP4 gap analysis was informed by surveys and interviews with infrastructure service providers and cohort service users, a scoping literature review and an expert stakeholder workshop. Our work highlights that, although several service providers supporting Large Medical Cohorts operate at international, European and national levels and collectively cover service needs across the entire lifecycle of cohort studies, current service provision often lacks scalability and effective coordination across providers. In addition, cohort service users are frequently unaware of the available service offers and of the appropriate access mechanisms, indicating limited visibility of existing service providers within the relevant research communities. The WP4 analysis further indicated that these shortcomings are best addressed by reinforcing and promoting improved coordination of the existing service landscape, rather than by investing in new infrastructures. In this context, the creation of a coordinated and integrated service package across European (e.g. ECRIN, BBMRI, ELIXIR, Euro-BioImaging, EBRAINS) and national service providers, combined with facilitated access mechanisms for cohort service users, would be sufficient to address the majority of infrastructure-related gaps and stakeholder needs identified in WP4. Such an approach would enhance service discoverability, improve efficiency and scalability, and support the long-term sustainability and impact of Large Medical Cohorts. The WP4 findings will be presented and extensively discussed with the leaders and partners of WP16 “New concept and sustainability” to ensure that the INTEGRATE-LMedC final proposals align with the different findings of preparatory WPs.

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ANNEX 1

Services constituting the five service clusters for Large Medical Cohorts.
More details are available in D4.1.

No.	Service Cluster	Types of Services Provided to Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC)
Services Cluster 1	Data Services	Data Management Plan
		CRF Development
		Data Management Services
		Data Monitoring/Quality Control
		Data Harmonization & Standard
		Data Integration
		Secondary Use of EHRs
		Cohort Data Secondary Use
		Cohort Data Sharing
		Biostatistics and Data Analysis
		Other Data Services
Services Cluster 2	Regulatory and Ethical Support	Ethics and Informed Consent
		Legal and Regulatory Advice
		Data Protection Advice
		Regulatory, Ethical Approvals & Amendments
Services Cluster 3	Methodology & Design	Design
		Methodology & Statistical Planning
		Protocol Review
		Cohort Protocol Registration
		Planning (advice, research support)
Services Cluster 4	Biobanking & OMICS	Biobanking & Sample Management
		OMICS Analysis
Services Cluster 5	Operational Support and Coordination	Conduct
		Patient Recruitment
		Patient Engagement
		Dissemination (e.g. catalogue)
		Training and Capacity Building

ANNEX 2

The data charting table for the extraction of relevant information from publications included in the scoping review was structured as follows:

- Publication title
- Publication DOI
- Specific geographic focus
(if yes fill in the region/country/continent)
- Focus on specific initiative
(if yes fill in the specific initiative - e.g., UK biobank, EHDS)
- Focus on specific disease *(if applicable)*
- Select Service Cluster *(drop-down list)*
- Cross-cutting / All clusters
- Data Services
- Regulatory and Ethical Support
- Methodology and Design
- Biobanking and OMICS
- Operational support and coordination
- Other services that cannot be classified under the clusters
- If applicable:
Service gaps in bulletpoints
- If applicable:
Service gaps explained with short text
(Use text directly from the publication to explain the service gaps you identified. Please not more than 4 paragraphs)
- Select User Group *(drop-down list)*
- All user groups
- Researcher managing a cohort
- Researcher re-using cohort data
- Patient / citizen representatives
- Regulators
- Funders
- Policymakers
- Other
- If applicable:
User needs in bulletpoints
- If applicable:
User needs explained with short text
(Use text directly from the publication to explain the user needs you identified. Please not more than 4 paragraphs)
- If applicable:
Challenges identified
- If applicable:
Recommendations mentioned